

Evaluation of Ranking & Matchmaking in Competition

A Simulation and Humanist Approach

Master Thesis

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Abstract

In recent years, there has been an increasing amount of complaints in the video game community regarding ranking and competition. Ranking systems can be evaluated with empirical study on game dataset. For sport and competition, there is a simple model suitable for simulation based research. Yet this approach is relatively absent from literature. The purpose of the thesis is double. First, I introduce the matchmaking overfitting hypothesis. I perform comparative studies between state-of-the-art rating systems, highlighting differences in behavior in challenging settings. In a second step, I present the experiment to a panel of experts in competition to measure how receptive they are to simulation.

Keywords Competition, Ranking, Bradley-Terry model, Simulation, steady state, Elo, Glicko, TrueSkill, OpenSkill

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*Ce que l'on conçoit bien s'énonce clairement, et les mots pour le dire arrivent aisément.*¹

Nicolas Boileau-Despréaux, L'art poétique (1674)

¹Whatever we conceive well, we express clearly, and words then flow with ease. Translation taken from <https://skwi.fr/2015/07/08/what-you-understand-well-you-enunciate-clearly/>

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1

Introduction

In this thesis, I propose to combine Simulation Based Research and Human Centered Approach. In simulation, one deals with a model. It is pure computation with little regard, not only for humans, but also for the "Real World". In Human Centered Design, people are at the center of the methodology. It focuses on a user in an interactive system and his needs to increase customer satisfaction. Often, it includes community participatory research. These methods seem opposed to each other. I argue that their differences are exactly what makes them valuable together. The motivation is to understand why simulation is a neglected approach in the fields despite well known models. This *marriage* turned out to be a powerful and meaningful one.

The work presented in this thesis takes its roots in complaints formulated against ranking and match-making algorithms by the gaming community on social networks. To address certain issues, I propose the *matchmaking overfitting hypothesis*. Simply put, can a ranking learn a bias introduced by a matchmaking algorithm? The key point is the interdependency between both notions. A Ranking infers the level of players based on game data. A matchmaking system generates and evaluates potential games to be played using a ranking. There is a loop: a ranking is used to generate games, which in turn are used to train a ranking. Overfitting in that context means that a ranking makes great predictions on the games it suggest itself as quality games. However, it could perform poorly on other potential matchups. This would not appear in a dataset. It is a snake eating its own tail.

This hypothesis is suited for simulation based research. First of all, in the context of competition in sports, there are well-known models for simulation. The domain uses and validates simulation. But more importantly, to study the bias of a dataset, one needs to control the entire data generation process. Simulation does this, a model controls everything happening in a run. When one knows in advance the bias in the data, it is relatively simple to measure if a ranking learned the bias. Alternatively, we can produce many different datasets by changing hyper-parameters and conduct comparative studies to evaluate ranking design and their resilience to the phenomenon.

After conducting experiments, I present a few selected one to a panel of expert in competition. The goal is to evaluate how receptive they are to simulation research. Do they understand the model? Does it fit their intuition and experience? What do they think of the design and the metrics used? To some extent, this is also related to the potential that simulation can have regarding the transmission of knowledge - its usage as an educational tool. Can scientists exchange and share their work with a targeted community

using simulated examples? This question addresses the thesis motivation - community complaints.

In Chapter 2, I provide an overview of the methodologies. What is simulation based research? How is it performed for competition? I place it within the context of recommendation system and from the perspective of Human Centered research. In Chapter 3, I present the tools used, the technical details of the research, and its implementation. You will find there the potential for future research and some limitation. Someone looking to challenge and critique my work should probably start here. In Chapter 4, you will find the details about experimentation. I focus mostly on the ideas and goals of the experimental design. Results should be reproducible with any tools, and should not be code dependent. A clear, yet simple, protocol is provided in that regard. It contains all the necessary modeling considerations and the run specifications for anyone looking to replicate the experiments. The chapter also covers my own analysis, interpretation, and conclusions of each experiments in dedicated subsections. In Chapter 5, I discuss the interaction with experts in the field, from the survey design to its conclusion. This might come as a surprise: to split the two methodologies into separate chapters in a thesis where the topic is about combining them, seems incoherent. There are multiple reasons for it. First, it represents the work. The studies were conducted and designed separately, the second following the first. The reader could be interested in, or referring to one independently. But more importantly, the benefit of including design research - involving participants with simulation research - is independent of the underlying *actual* simulation research questions and experiments. It does not matter what I was interested in or the content of my research. What matters is the nature of the *Human - Simulation* interaction, and how does the two benefit from each other. But before all of this, I strongly recommend to read section 1.1, which present the context of my research, and section 1.3 where the terminology about ranking and competition is introduced.

1.1 Motivation

I love games and sports, and I do watch a lot of events. I love competition and did measure myself against other contestants in several titles. I even earned a bit of money from it as player, coach, analyst and commentator. In competition, rankings are everywhere. They are a great tool to compare athletes against each other, which is exactly the nature of competition. I am and have been ranked in many different games.

In 2023, I have seen many complaints over the internet about ranking and seeding in video game competitions. One of the frequent conversations surrounding League of Legend¹ matchmaking is the *Loser Queue Theory*. Some players believe that Riot matches losing player together with a presumed intention to make them lose even more. Doing this manipulates the ranking, leading to *hard-stuck*² and *boosted*³ players. I do not believe in this theory nor even understand what it is supposed to explain. But I can accept that people have a horrible experience in a game due to a bad competitive ecosystem. It is hard to formulate exactly a problem in a technical field. To me, the Loser Queue Theory does not describe a malicious algorithm, it expresses an unpleasant human experience.

In a Reddit post⁴, user *renecotyfanboy*, a French PhD student in astrophysics (as he presents himself), tries to disprove the theory. Two days later, a Twitter thread⁵ from *@AnalyseStatLOL* performed additional study and provide nuances to the results. The works are reasonably well documented, especially for social media posts. My issues are regarding the dataset and a debatable hypothesis. They use games from the master tier level, the 1% highest ranked players⁶. It's not a bad dataset, but why not use a more representative one? Whatever conclusion you draw from it is limited to a minority of gamers. Also, they

¹A popular esports title of the MOBA genre

²A player whom ranking is significantly underrated

³A player who's ranking is significantly overrated

⁴www.reddit.com/r/leagueoflegends/comments/15k2nw4/existence_of_loser_queue_a_statistical_analysis/

⁵<https://x.com/AnalyseStatLOL/status/1688738885944119296>

⁶rank distribution can be seen at <https://www.leagueofgraphs.com/rankings/rank-distribution>

use the Elo algorithm to process the data and rank the players. It is an arbitrary choice. At the time, there was no documentation of which method Riot⁷ ⁸ used to rank their customers. But today we know it is *TrueSkill2*⁹¹⁰. Interesting work, but not conclusive in my eyes. It does highlight that the community is not happy about the state of the game and tries itself to find answers to questions and problematics.

On May 25th 2023, *NER0cs* posted on HLTV a blog¹¹ criticizing the usage of seeding in the biggest Counter-strike event of the year, the Major. He points out that the rank correlation between the seeding and the final standing was below 0 in several top events. He recommends changing the seeding procedure. I was chocked and still am chocked. My interpretation of a negative rank correlation between seeding and final standing is the following one: The ranking used for initial seeds was not of good quality. It fails to make accurate predictions. The athletes involved in the tournament were able to perform independently of their initial seeds. It was an unbiased competition. My conclusion is that the ranking performs poorly, not the seeds. My recommendation would be to improve the ranking design. I want to add a serious concern I have. Personally, I consider **Changing the seeding procedure to get desired results** match fixing! The document 'CETS - 215' by the Council of Europe¹² stipulates:

"[...] sport, based on fair and equal competition, is unpredictable in nature and requires unethical practices and behaviour in sport to be forcefully and effectively countered [...]"

These posts not only showed practical issues, but raised a more profound question. How does one perform study on ranking? What should be measured? Which data matters, and which methodology to use?

I expected to find answers to those questions in scientific papers. But no. Turns out, different systems are evaluated with different metrics and different methodologies. Some use datasets and evaluate game score prediction. Other uses mathematical definition and theorem proof. Others perform simulations and verify expected behavior. Diversity in methods is great. It is an asset to tackle problems from multiple perspectives and increase the meaning of the object under study. But I see a segregation: Elo with mathematical and simulation supports versus TrueSkill and OpenSkill with empirical support.

In the following section, I explain more precisely a hypothesis of mine. It is an idea that emerged exploring the state-of-the-art. Convergence - a word frequently used to describe ranking's behavior - seems to be abusively interpreted in certain contexts.

1.2 The Problematic: Matchmaking Overfitting

In data driven research, fine-tuning a model to avoid over- or under-fitting is crucial. This is relatively absent from literature about rankings in competition. As you may have realized, I look for **over**, not underfitting. Why so?

Overfitting risk increases with an increasing number of parameters in a model. People complain more about TrueSkill than Elo, the first uses more value to rate players. The uniqueness of a stationary distribution is a property that the Elo system can exhibit depending on the matchmaking. Simply put, the game generation procedure can impact the resulting ranking, its convergence.

For some reason, matchmaking matters when ranking players. It is possible to rank players with fewer parameters than the amount there is in the criticized systems. Research tends to not track rigorously overfitting.

⁷Many assumes it is an Elo rating system in LoL, but official sources explicitly state that the system used is kept secret

⁸<https://support-leagueoflegends.Riotgames.com/hc/en-us/articles/4405781372051-MMR-Rank-and-LP>

⁹<https://www.sportskeeda.com/esports/league-legends-season-14-new-mmr-trueskill-2-systems-explained#>

¹⁰My guess would be that at the time of the reddit post, they used TrueSkill

¹¹<https://www.hltv.org/news/36097/valves-swiss-system-under-the-microscope>

¹²<https://rm.coe.int/16801cdd7e>

Thus, the *matchmaking overfitting hypothesis*.

1.3 Definitions

- **Ranking** Any algorithm used to sort and compare players. They implement a relationship between its elements and their respective ratings. Examples are: Elo, Glicko, TrueSkill etc.
- **Rating** The value assigned by a ranking to a player. Value is to be understood largely. Elo uses a single integer or float, Glicko models players with a mean and a variance, while Glicko2 stores a triplet mean, variance and volatility.
- **Scheduler** Any algorithm that generates games between participants. In this thesis, we distinguish between competition (typical in sport) and matchmaking (common in video games). A given player can be assigned to many games that need to be organized and played at different times, leading to the scheduling problem.
- **Competition** Scheduler *bounded in time and space*. A competition has a start and an end, a finite limited number of participants, and often, a final standing based on game outcome during the event (a winner, 2nd place, etc.). To avoid confusion with the general notion of competition in sport, I use **Format, Tournament** to precise the context of Scheduler when it is needed. Examples are: Single Elimination Bracket, Double Elimination Bracket, Round Robin, Swiss Round Robin.
- **Matchmaking** Scheduler not bounded in time nor space. A participant can join at will, play when he wants, and take any extended pause. A practical way to implement live matchmaking is with *First-in, First-out Queue*. This would minimize the waiting time of players but can lead to a very unpleasant gaming experience. Better practices are: *Skilled Based Matchmaking* and *Engagement Optimized Matchmaking*.
- **Player** Players are the participants of games, the elements ranked in a ranking. It is the notion of athletes competing against each other.
- **Game** In the thesis, the notion of game is an encounter between players. It is not a specific title or discipline. We do not speak here about the Chess game or Hockey. The game mode refers to the way players interact with each other. A duel would be a one-versus-one game. In League of Legend and Counter-Strike, players are split into two teams of 5 members each. We refer to many-versus-many game mode.
- **Score** The score is the game outcome. In versus mode, the score can be a win, a loss or a draw. In race or free-for-all mode, the score is a value representing an achievement, like a list of final placements.
- **Seed** The seed is an integer assigned to a participant in a competition. The seeding is used to make arbitrary decisions without bias towards participants. For example, in an 8-player single elimination bracket, a common way to pair the first round is to match **seed 1** versus **seed 8**. It is frequent to use a ranking for seeding purposes. But seed can be random.
- **Solver** It is a function that assigns a score to a game. A simple solver is a random one that gives 50% of the time a win and otherwise a loss. In simulation, the solver is a core component and implements a model. In the one-versus-one game mode, a solver acts as a pairwise comparison.
- **Strength** or **Skill** is an attribute of *Player* that capture his level and ability to perform in games. In this thesis, I focus on a simple model where strength is a single integer value; the higher it is, the better the player is and the more likely he is to win games.
- **Consensus Ranking** is the ranking where players are sorted by their strength. It fits the intuition of what a ranking should look like.

2

Methodology

2.1 Simulation Based Research

The website of the Eastern Switzerland University of Applied Science gives an excellent introduction to the topic. The Institute of Modeling and Simulation states¹:

In a world characterised by growing complexity, the IMS Institute of Modelling and Simulation facilitates better decision-making by fostering a deeper understanding of systematic relationships, examining relevant scenarios and identifying optimum solutions.

Our support consists of developing specific (if possible, mathematical) models of the decision-making situation. These then serve either as a 'laboratory environment' for evaluating possible solutions together with decision-makers, or as the basis for mathematical optimization.

I want to highlight several keywords. **Models** define a **laboratory** in which one performs experimental studies. This notion is elaborated in section 2.1.1. The important point is that simulation is a controlled environment with clearly defined behaviors. "**Deeper understanding of systematic relationships**", the goal of research is not the discovery of fundamental laws. Measuring gravity has little meaning in simulation. Research questions are oriented towards understanding a system, or alternatively, for **optimization**. I am not convinced that it is always about relationships. I lack experience, but my intuition tells me it is not limited to it. However, this thesis, indeed, is about understanding a systemic relationship, the one between a matchmaking algorithm and a ranking. I can imagine that the reason to perform simulation based research arises from an inherent relationship that cannot be studied otherwise. Frequently this method appears because we deal with high **complexity**, and the multiplication of **scenarios** is an attack angle. Sometimes simulation is just a way to reduce research costs.

Simulation should be the last resort. When other *traditional* approaches cannot answer the problem, simulation becomes an option. In [18] A. Maria gives a great introduction to the methodology. Sections 2.1.1, 2.1.2 and 2.1.3 summarize the important aspects and are heavily based on this paper.

¹<https://www.ost.ch/en/research-and-consulting-services/technology/industrial-engineering/ims-institute-of-modelling-and-simulation>

2.1.1 Modeling

A model is a simple, ideal, representation of the world. It is an abstraction of an object under study. Typically, a model is manipulated with logic and mathematical operations to make predictions. Predictions that can be observed in the real world tend to validate a model. Observations that cannot be explained by a model tend to invalidate or propose a modified version of the said model. In a Simulation, the model is the "real world". It describes the *laws/rules* that dictate the behavior of objects and their interactions.

Models give the feeling to be arbitrary. A none-justified, fantasist universe. Many models can be studied; most are not interesting at all. The model purpose is the opposite of fantasy. It limits the options. It defines the range of what is possible. Likewise, it restricts what happens in an environment that would otherwise be chaotic and arbitrary.

Models can be data driven or theoretically derived. Models can be deterministic or stochastic. Important for simulation is its validity. A well-conducted research can be entirely invalidated by its model. My study is based on the Bradley-Terry model[2], and I perform simulation as presented in [1]. I studied largely deployed and used ranking algorithms and common formats of competition. Section 2.4 presents the state-of-the-art for systems of interest. When it comes to modeling, I do propose one tournament format. I claim it is of interest, with remarkable properties. Section 4.3 covers the motivation, modeling steps, up to mathematical proof and concept validations.

2.1.2 Simulation

Simulation studies a real system, something of interest for us in the real world. This can be a production chain, an object specification and in our case, rankings and scheduler. Elo exists, so does the single elimination bracket. Simulation consists in a challenging environment, defined by a model. The conclusions we draw are not about the real world, but rather about the system.

Figure 2.1 illustrates the iterative nature of simulation. Based on previous results, the system is altered. It is, in my eyes, an extremely important process in simulation. To analyze results and draw conclusions, the key ingredient is the understanding of the model. After all, it is the core of the engine that produces the results. Building iterative models allows us to understand increasing complexity by having intermediate steps to refer to and compare results.

If someone changes the system, the model, the experimental protocol and all the hyperparameters at once, how do you interpret the results? What conclusion do you draw from it? Were the results induced by the system changes or the model alteration ?

Modeling modern online competition can be quite complex: often gaming involves players in live skilled base matchmaking, many-versus-many game mode with potential roles and learning curves, unbalance and meta shift. Most of the components can be implemented, and there are techniques to simulate it. However, each piece needs to be understood separately before combining them together. In chapter 4 I describe the simplest run I performed alongside a *goal* to reach. The presented experiments are in between steps.

Figure 2.1: Simulation Based Research

The simulation acts as a laboratory - a controlled environment - where experimentation are performed. Important to note that conclusion do not address the *real world* rather a system under study. Image source: [18].

2.1.3 Research

[18] describe the following 11 steps of simulation based research. They are not always all possible nor necessary, but they offer a logical approach to avoid pitfalls. Regarding each of the steps, I add my own comments about their meaning and relevance regarding the topic of my research, *Ranking in Competition*.

- Step 1. **Identify the problem:** There are community complaints and doubts about the quality of ranking in places. Details about this can be found in 1.1.
- Step 2. **Formulate the problem:** I suggest a potential cause: *matchmaking overfitting*. The hypothesis as the advantage to explain both the problem and why the problem arises. Ranking do not capture the player level, but the scheduler domain, thus the complain from players. It appears because overfitting in the context of competition is overlooked. More in section 1.2.
- Step 3. **Collect and process real system data:** I study state-of-the-art ranking and scheduling algorithm (section 2.4). The parameters of the systems are the default ones, as suggested by authors.
- Step 4. **Formulate and develop a model:** I use the Bradley-Terry Model for modeling players level and game outcomes. I do develop one scheduler model for skilled-based matchmaking, presented in section 4.3.
- Step 5. **Validate the model:** The Bradley-Terry model is a famous and commonly used model for simulation. It is already validated by decades of usage. I discuss the simulation tool's validity and its implementation in section 3.3. The proposed scheduler model is validated in section 4.3.5.

- **Step 6. Document the model for future use:** All the experiences are presented in chapter 4. Each of them as a subsection called *Protocol*. It consists in a short paragraph with all the necessary information to reproduce the results.
- **Step 7. Select appropriate experimental design:** To study the interplay of ranking and scheduler I designed a very simple setup, "RSSC" explained in the baseline section 4.1.
- **Step 8. Establish experimental conditions for runs:** Elements that are not necessary to reproduce the experiment, but important to understand the simulation, are discussed in dedicated *Motivation & goals* subsection of chapter 4. The general conditions are the following: ranking with no prior knowledge, player of constant skills following a Gaussian distribution, random initial seeds.
- **Step 9. Perform simulation runs:** Simulations were performed in Jupyter notebooks, available as additional material to the thesis (with the resulting synthetic datasets).
- **Step 10. Interpret and present results:** Results are presented in dedicated subsections of chapter 4.
- **Step 11. Recommend further course of actions** For my own hypothesis, the direction of research is dictated by an *ultimate question* presented in section 4.0.2. However, further courses of action suggested by experts of competition are presented in section 5.3.2.

Steps 1 and 2 are not specific to simulation, but generally related to research. Sometimes, simulation does help to identify a problem. For example, Graham Pitt² showed that the 8th-best team does not qualify in the CS:GO major format using a deterministic model - the highest seed wins games. Collecting real data is important for system tuning and sometimes to develop data driven models. Here, I use common algorithms and did no hyperparameter's optimization. I always selected default behavior. This means that the simulation does not address a particular use case. It is more of a theoretical research. Step 5 can be seen as specific. In other methods, the validation of a model comes at the end of experimentation, or even in discussion and conclusion. Here the validation comes before any run and needs to be carefully documented. Regarding conclusion, I already stated that any interpretation is about the system understanding, not the real world. And this is critical for the last steps. The experimental design, the metric, and the run condition must be approached with this in mind. Otherwise, no conclusion can be drawn.

2.2 Recommendation System Simulation

A matchmaking algorithm can be seen as a recommendation system. It does propose games and evaluate their quality, which ones are preferred. The same can be said about rankings. They list players in a preferred order. Interesting is that simulation is accepted and performed in the context of competition. But not so much for recommendation system. The main reason is the lack of models. Or the lack of consensus surrounding their validity.

[3] highlights two challenges regarding modelings. One for the consumer choice, the selection of item among recommendations. I interpret this as the outcome of an event. This is related to the notion of Solver in my thesis. The second point is the access of a user to items. What is presented to whom? In my work, I identify this with the scheduler.

SimuRec[8] is an ongoing workshop whose goal is to lay the foundation for simulation based research for various types of recommender systems. It is an ongoing project, lasting for several years already. The authors come from various research areas and interests. Among them: Human centered perspective, impacts of methods on individuals and society, evaluation bias, fairness properties, quality of recommendation.

Simulation research is not always possible or accepted. Fields of research do not always have consensual models. But it is a today challenge and aspiration to enhance simulation potential and usage.

²<https://x.com/messioso/status/1644389658942373899>

2.3 Simulation for Competition

In 2017, D. Aldous published a paper titled *Elo Ratings and the Sports Model: A Neglected Topic In Applied Probability*?[1]. The paper presents a model for simulation, metrics, examples of runs and questions to work on. There is also discussion about *Statistical Analysis* and *Probability in the Real World*. The paper can be seen as a foundation, or cornerstone, of my thesis. I designed my simulation tool based on models presented. The title itself reinforces the initial motivation. Why is there so little simulation based research in the field when there is a consensus on how to perform it and challenging questions?

2.3.1 MMBench

MMBench[17] is a benchmark framework to evaluate and compare ranking systems. It offers game developers the ability to identify bottlenecks in their systems and adapt parameters to different game modes.

The tool supports multiple game modes (one-versus-one, many-versus-many, Battle Royal and Teamed Battle Royal) and the most important rating systems (Elo, Glicko and TrueSkill). The evaluation takes as input game data or uses a *Match Generator* module to produce synthetic data. This simulation module can be tuned by the *Skill Generator*³ and the *Outcome Generator*⁴. The simulation allows direct comparison of the inferred ratings with the ground truth.

While MMBench looks like an ideal tool, It does not enable the research question I had in the first place. It has fewer customization options. The main limitation I see, reading the paper, is the lack of interaction between a system under test, and the model. Especially, MMBench does not seem to have a module to specify **who plays against whom?**. Yet, this is a needed feature to study my research question: **Can a ranking overfit the matchmaking domain?**

For This reason, I chose to build my own custom simulation tool (see chapter 3).

2.4 State-of-the-art

Arpad E. Elo [9] proposed in 1979 his famous rating system. Elo is still today a common choice in many different title. The FIFA / Coca-Cola World Ranking⁵ for international football is a variation of the Elo introducing game weight. League of Legend Power Ranking⁶ alters team ratings with a league rating to build an international Elo-based ranking. M. E. Glickman extended Elo by modeling the player's rating with Gaussian values in his Glicko system [11]. He recently introduced the notion of volatility with Glicko2 [10]. Glicko is typically used in online chess platforms⁷. Elo and Glicko are limited by their use case, the one-versus-one game mode. For general game mode and ratings, TrueSkill [13] introduced a novel approach based on factor graph. TrueSkill2 [19] is a recent improvement. OpenSkill [24] is a Bayesian inference system implementing ratings for the Bradley-Terry [2], Thurstone-Mosteller [5] and Plackett-Luce [23] models.

For sport competition, standard pairing systems include: Round Robin [21], Swiss Round [12], Single and Double Elimination Bracket. The impact of tournaments on player performances is illustrated in [22]. It distinguish between fairness and balance. For video games and online matchmaking, encouraged practices are competitive balance [20] and Engagement Optimized matchmaking[4]. In [14] P.E. Jabin studied the interaction of the Elo and a skilled based matchmaking. It highlights the difficulty of mathematically

³The paper refers to three distributions: normal, uniform and the power-law distribution

⁴With the choices of a deterministic or non-deterministic simulation

⁵<https://inside.fifa.com/fifa-world-ranking/procedure-men>

⁶<https://lsolesports.com/en-GB/news/dev-diary-unveiling-the-global-power-rankings>

⁷https://support.chess.com/en/articles/8566476-how-do-ratings-work-on-chess-com#h_64e2c8e644

studying the uniqueness of a stationary distribution in the Elo on a skilled based matchmaking case. Simulation methods to study ranking in sports are summarized by D. Aldous in [1] and illustrated for simple Elo convergence by A. Krifa in [16].

In [6] and [7] A. Dehpanah explores validation metrics for rating systems in different game modes. In simulation based research, we can compare a ranking learning with a ground truth ranking using the Kendall rank correlation [15].

3

RSTT Package

3.1 Presentation

RSTT stands for Ranking Simulation Testing Tool, and is exactly that: A tool to test ranking through simulation. It was originally developed to ease the coding of simple experiments of my own. But as experiments became bigger and more complex, so did the package.

The goal of RSTT is to enable research about competition integrity. A special focus was put on the study of steady state of ranking regarding different formats of competition and player behavior. It offers close to complete control over all parameters behind the generation of a synthetic game dataset.

With the package, a lot of the workload in simulation based research is shifted from the coding of a simulation to the analysis of the data. This was achieved by identifying needed components of a competition simulation and handling all their interactions at the highest level of abstraction. In turn, coding a simulation is reduced to specifying the parameters (the component) and ordering events (the protocol); the run itself is performed by the package.

This thesis is not about the development of the package¹; however, the research conducted relies heavily on it. This chapter provides all the information necessary to understand the work and build a critical opinion on it. The following sections describe implementation choices, concepts in place, the validation process of the package, and how it can be used.

3.2 Implementation

3.2.1 Language Choice

The package is implemented in Python. The language choice was motivated by the target audience: people who analyze data - data scientists, mathematicians, etc. This means that one can generate a synthetic dataset and analyze it in one single place, like a Jupyter notebook, for example. On the downside of this choice is the performance resulting from an interpreted language (see section 3.4.4).

¹The implementation was also not part of the thesis, neither in scope nor time. During the master thesis, limited modifications were done to the package.

Another reason is the object of interest: Rankings. There are publicly available Python implementations of TrueSkill² and OpenSkill³.

3.2.2 Design

The package, and any simulation based on it, relies on the following notion (also defined in section 1.3). Figure 3.1 shows UML class diagrams.

- **Ranking** is a *Composition over Inheritance* class that stores "standing", "datamodel", "inferer" and an "observer". The class responsibility is to maintain the correct ordering of players in the standing and offer a convenient user interface.
- **Datamodel** A variant of default dictionary where keys are **Player** and values are **Rating**. It accepts functions of the key as default values. A datamodel also provides an ordinal() method to convert a rating into a float value.
- **Standing** A list-dictionary hybrid container. It stores a triplet (rank, item, value). Ranks are integer from 0 to n, items are Player and values are float used to sort the standing. In a ranking class, the values in the standing match the datamodel.ordinal() returned values.
- **Backend** A statistical inference tool to compute ratings from game data. It is defined as an interface that provides a rate() function.
- **Handler** A game pre- and post-processing component. It is defined as an interface that provides an handle_observations() function.
- **Scheduler** An automated *Game* generation protocol.
- **Game** models an encounter of *Player* with an outcome - a **Score**.
- **Player** are the common elements *Ranking/Scheduler/Game share*. Player plays *Game* and gets rated by *Ranking*. A Player has a level() methods that returns values to compute game outcomes.
- **Solver** is the core of a simulation. It is the component that assign a *Score* to a *Game*. Usually by looking at the *Player* models, like their respective **levels**.

Any simulation in RSTT is a composition of at least 'Game', 'Solver' and 'Player'. The research I performed used also 'Competition' class to generate games and 'Ranking' to rate Player.

The package is meant to enable research and not to constrain the simulation design by its features' limitations. This means users have a relative flexibility to play with their own component that fits in the tool.

This was achieved by implementing the notions at a high level of abstraction. In most cases it is sufficient to inherit from an existing class and override a few methods to enrich the behavior of the simulation.

Another design feature is **type restriction**, which Python does not support by default. This is important in the case of developers who integrate their own component into the framework. It ensures that functionalities are used on the correct data structure and that the components interact the way they were designed to. The entire package uses typing⁴ for function annotations, and typeguard⁵ for runtime type-checking.

The package defines 'Protocol'⁶ and uses Duck-Typing to give more freedom than inheritance would.

²<https://trueskill.org>

³<https://openskill.me/en/stable/installation.html>

⁴<https://docs.python.org/3/library/typing.html>

⁵<https://peps.python.org/pep-0647/>

⁶interface in other object-oriented programming languages

Figure 3.1: Class diagram of the RSTT package. Core concepts of the simulation are Player, Game and solver. They interact with each other by the means of the Game.play(), Solver.solve() and Player.level() methods. Competition and Ranking reflect the systems under study.

3.3 Validation

I am confident in my results and their scientific relevance. The base model is simple to implement. I have performed unit testing⁷. Before any experimentation, I run model validation. When I run multiple times the same experiment, I get consistent results. I can use my tool to verify claims made in publication. I can reproduce results from others with a few line of code using the RSTT framework.

3.3.1 Reproducibility of Results

I illustrate here that with the RSTT package it is possible to run experiments and reproduce published simulations and results.

A. Krifa shows in [16] a simple Elo convergence simulation. The example is relevant to the thesis because: (1) It studies long-term convergence. (2) It manipulates initial seeding. Figure 3.2 shows the original diagram, the caption is a copy-paste of the setting specification in the paper. Figure 3.3 shows the RSTT version.

⁷<https://docs.python.org/3/library/unittest.html>

Figure 3.2: This graph shows the Elo evolution over 1000 games of two players A and B, A has a $p = b(\rho_1\rho_2)$ chance of winning against B. ρ is meant to be the 'true' (theoretical) force of a player; $b(\rho_1\rho_2)$ is what we will name the 'natural' probability of A winning against B. Here we have $\rho_1 = 1500$, $\rho_2 = 700$ and the players start with 1000 and 1200 Elo respectively. Source: [16], page 10.

Figure 3.3: RSTT simulation using the same setting as in Figure 3.2. We observe similar results with different code implementations. The run is stochastic, and no seed was specified to the random generator in the RSTT version. The simulation tool did not need fine-tuning of hyperparameters. The code is available in appendix A.1.

3.4 Usage

3.4.1 Example

For simple simulation, one usually needs a population of players, a scheduler to generate games, and a solver to decide the outcome of encounters. To make it interesting, a ranking can be updated and compared to the ground truth implied by the model. Figure 3.4 illustrates a basic usage of the `rstt` package, with no parameters' specification. The population is generated using a Gaussian distribution. It is possible to fine-tune the mean and variance of the player's level. It is possible to fine-tune the hyperparameters of the Elo ranking.

```
# some player
population = Player.create(nb=16)

# a ranking
elo = BasicElo(name='Elo Ranking', players=population)

# display the ranking to the standard output
elo.plot()

# create a competition - we specify the players seedings and the solver use to play the games
tournament = SingleEliminationBracket(name='RSTT World Cup 2024', seeding=elo, solver=LogSolver())

# register player - the seedings do not define the participants, unranked participants get assigned lower seeds
tournament.registration(population)

# play the tournament
tournament.run()

# update the ranking based on the game played
elo.update(games=tournament.games())

# display the updated ranking
elo.plot()

# the LogSolver implies a Ranking based on 'the real level' of players
truth = BTRanking(name='Consensus Ranking', players=population)
truth.plot()
```

Figure 3.4: We can recognize behind the variable the related notion of Player (population), Scheduler (tournament), Solver (LogSolver()) and rankings (elo, truth). We do not see the notion of Game. The game mode is *one-versus-one*. The mode is the consequences of the scheduler choice (Single Elimination Bracket) and the registration of Player (rather than team of Player).

Additional material to the thesis include tutorial notebooks of the package. They focus on the user interface of the classes and the different model implementation. It can be useful to understand experimental code.

I implemented myself an Elo⁸ and Glicko⁹ *Backend*. TrueSkill and OpenSkill have official Python distribution, Figure 3.5 shows how to integrate OpenSkill in the RSTT framework by inheritance from the *Ranking* class. It is not necessary to write *predict* and *quality* methods. That depends on what you want to measure and if you prefer to interact with the ranking rather than the ranking.backend (openskill.models instance).

Testing Python implemented ranking system is straight forward. If there is no Python distribution, one option is to write an observer (*in the code: handler*) that dumps formatted game data in a file (for example .csv or .json) and reads updated ratings from another one. Additionally, a dummy *backend* needs to launch an external process (running the actual system), and its `rate()` methods should signal the process to read the game date file and write back the updated ratings.

⁸Implementation follows the wikipedia description. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Elo_rating_system

⁹The implementation rigorously follows Dr. Mark E. Glickmann specification. It was also tested with the author's computation example

```

class BasicOS(Ranking):
    def __init__(self, name: str='', model=None, players=None):
        super().__init__(name=name,
                        standing=Standing(),
                        datamodel=GaussianModel(factory=lambda x: model.rating(name=x.name)),
                        backend=model,
                        handler=GameByGame(),
                        players=players)

    def predict(self, game) -> float:
        _, teams_as_ratings, _, _ = self.handler.match_formatting(datamodel=self.datamodel, game=game)
        return self.backend.predict_win(teams_as_ratings)[0]

    def quality(self, game) -> float:
        _, teams_as_ratings, _, _ = self.handler.match_formatting(datamodel=self.datamodel, game=game)
        return self.backend.predict_draw(teams_as_ratings)

```

Figure 3.5: RSTT integration example with the OpenSkill library; openskill.models provide multiple technique to rate players based on game outcome. The experiment in chapter 4 uses this code with the parameter: model=openskill.models.PlackettLuce()

3.4.2 Access

The package is available upon request from the author¹⁰. Note that TrueSkill¹¹ usage requires a license. The package has auto generated documentation using numPy¹² style docstring and sphinx¹³. The code comments issues, feature enhancement, performances bottlenecks and some unresolved bugs. The code comments includes literature and web references to implemented models. I did perform unit testing to ensure code specifications. I did work on performances benchmark and optimization.

3.4.3 Quality

To ensure minimal standards of code quality, I followed software development principles such as *Liskov Substitution*, *Dependency Inversion* or design patterns such as *Decorator* and *Delegation*. Adhering to these good practices enabled me to write robust code that allowed me to proceed smoothly with my simulations. In fact, most of the error was due to inappropriate usage of the package rather than a bug within RSTT itself.

As an example, the "**Must be a new event**" error in the package ensures dataset integrity. Player instances track automatically games they play and events they participated in. Events must have a name to identify them, and, for example, it is not possible to participate twice in the *World Cup 1998*. It is impossible to execute accidentally¹⁴ the following code portion twice.

```

# parameter
year = 1998

# schedule an event
event = SingleEliminationBracket(name=f'World Cup - {year}',
                                seeding=ranking,
                                solver=solver)

# enroll competitors

```

¹⁰send an email to: davidbucherdev@gmail.com

¹¹<https://github.com/sublee/trueskill/blob/master/LICENSE>

¹²<https://numpydoc.readthedocs.io/en/latest/format.html>

¹³<https://www.sphinx-doc.org/en/master/index.html>

¹⁴by copy-paste or running a second time the same cell in a notebook

```

event.registration(ranking.players())

# play the tournament
event.run()

# update the ranking based on game results
ranking.update(games=event.games())

```

An error is raised the second time `cup.run()` is executed, before the `ranking.update()` is called¹⁵. The variable `year` needs to be updated before to avoid errors (or directly the 'name' parameter at event instantiation).

It is possible to update twice the ranking based on the same event games. You can call `ranking.update(...)` as many times as you want. But it needs to be explicitly written so without rerunning the event. The package does not allow an event to have multiple outcomes simultaneously. I have lost hours of computations and large datasets due to this feature. Rightfully so, because what I was doing made no sense.

In a stochastic environment, if we play multiple times the same event¹⁶ we can observe different results. The diversity of results can be interesting and is possible to study with the package. However, it needs to be explicit in the code by using the `Player.reset()`¹⁷ method in between event reruns.

3.4.4 Code Review

I used `pyinstrument`¹⁸ to identify bottlenecks in edge-case scenarios. I compared different ranking designs (as an abstract component of RSTT. I am not talking about Elo versus Glicko here) and sorting protocol. All of this is irrelevant to the thesis. The package performs probably faster than what we can expect from an interpreted simulation tool, but significantly slower than what we hope.

The package is bigger than the code needed for the experimentation. To review the thesis, it is not necessarily needed to review the entire package. Most of the features are not used. As a code profiler, `pyinstrument` tracks the call of each code section. This helps to identify which function is actually executed.

To have a deeper understanding of the simulation presented in chapter 4, you can take a look into the code analysis I performed (c.f. appendix B.2). It gives a decent glimpse of what happens under the hood. It follows the package calls in the *rssc protocol*, a code segment present in all my simulations.

¹⁵This can otherwise lead to ill-tuned ranking

¹⁶With identical initial state, i.e. same seeding, same player strength etc.

¹⁷method that clears a player's history.

¹⁸<https://pyinstrument.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

4

Experience

In this chapter, I present some of the most interesting experiences I have designed in my journey. 4.0.1 describes the first step I took in simulation. 4.0.2 presents a practical experiment to achieve, a sort of direction to keep the work coherent. In 4.3 I introduce a simple matchmaking model I propose. I claim it is an interesting and relevant object of research. In 4.2, 4.4 and 4.5 I detail three experiments of particular interest. I have presented all three to a panel of experts in competition to collect opinions and measure if it is of interest also from their perspective.

4.0.1 Starting Point

The very first system I studied was ranking in a two player base, one-versus-one game environment. It is the simplest case I could imagine. In this system a ranking is a function that maps an arbitrary string of results (for example: *wlwlwlllw...* where 'w' stands for 'win' and 'l' stands for 'lose') to a pair of ratings (*rating_1*, *rating_2*). The string is the input, and the ratings' pair, the output of the algorithm. This setting is borderline simulation. There is no player model, no distribution of skills, no matchmaking, no solver. Really just a function with input and output. There are however two parameters, the length of the input (how many characters) and the ratio between the 'w' and the 'l'¹.

The metrics that I found the most interesting in this setting is to measure the distribution of a *distance(rating_1, rating_2)* when the length of the string and the ratio *w/l* are kept constant. The question behind this design is: what happens to a ranking system when I change the order of the game presented? I went as far as developing an interactive user interface solely for this experimentation.

In regard to my hypothesis **Matchmaking overfitting**, there is no matchmaking. There is not a component that takes a player base and matches them together with the intention of playing a game. But there is a notion of history - the ordering of games, which is something that matchmaking does impact. How much are the ratings impacted by the last few games versus the *wl-strings* in its entire form?

¹Unrelated but interesting to point out that during my Bachelor thesis I worked on similar data - I called them 'wl-string'

4.0.2 The Direction, The Final Experimentation

Ultimately, behind the **matchmaking overfitting** hypothesis, stand practical problems I try to identify and solve. In a tweet, RiotPhroxzon addresses the **losers queue** issues. He explicitly states that they (at Riot) do not match on purpose underperforming players together to make them lose more games (in the video game League of Legend). His tweet states:

Sure there are games where your teammates play poorly, that's just the nature of a 5v5 game. In the long run, you're the only common factor and the only one responsible for your rating is you. If you took an "unwinnable" game and replayed it with any Challenger in your spot, it would probably result in a win.²

Although it is a reasonable statement in itself, the behavior of a ranking is something to be assessed. Are you indeed the only one responsible for your rating? *If you took an "unwinnable" game and replayed it with any Challenger³ in your spot* is a simulation protocol. The fact those games would result in wins is not debatable in itself, but the question is, if those games were wins, would it result in rating improvement?

However, the simulation model is quite complex. 5 versus 5 is harder to simulate than one-versus-one. The author introduces the notion of a player with time-varying strength, and more precisely, learning and improving from game experience and losses. All of this is possible. But one needs a clear understanding of each component individually, before combining them.

At the time of writing the thesis, I consider myself halfway from the start to this goal. I have explored a lot of the one-versus-one case regarding many different ranking design and matchmaking approaches. I have also tested players and metrics regarding time-varying levels. Furthermore, I have started the validation process of solver involving multiple players in two separate teams within a game.

4.1 Baseline

The Bradley-Terry model implies a Consensus Ranking based on the strength value of the players. I have mentioned that Elo has a unique stationary distribution. This means that the ranking state over a long time is independent of the initial condition. It should 'always' reach a state similar to the consensus ranking. In figure 4.1 we can see the convergence of the Elo system under three different conditions. It is an RSTT simulation using the following parameters:

- **Player** 64 players of constant skill draw from a Gaussian distribution $X \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu = 1500, \sigma^2 = 500)$.
- **game mode** one-versus-one.
- **Solver** The LogSolver() with a default $base = 10$ and logistic constant $lc = 400$. It computes win probability⁴

$$\mathbb{P}(A \text{ beats } B) = \frac{1}{base \frac{-(A.level() - B.level())}{lc}}$$

- **Ranking** The Elo rating system with $K = 20$, $lc = 400$ and default rating 1500.
- **Scheduler** It is a comparative run where the scheduler is the varying parameter.
- **interaction** RSSC loop described below. depth=160.

²<https://x.com/RiotPhroxzon/status/1756511358571643286>

³a rank corresponding to a few hundred best players among millions in a given region

⁴<https://wismuth.com/elo/calculator.html>

Figure 4.1: Behavior of Elo regarding different tournament formats, and different initial conditions. (A) is the best case scenario, when the ranking knows in advance the ground truth. (B) is the normal case, where the ranking has no prior knowledge and all players have the same initial ratings of 1500. (C) shows a worst-case scenario, the player at rank i in the consensus ranking is assigned an Elo value equal to the strength of the player at rank $n-i$, where n is the number of players.

The way all these objects interact with each other in the simulation is defined in by the *RSSC*⁵ loop. It is a function that takes as input a tuple (ranking R , scheduler C , solver S , depth D) and outputs a dataset. All players in the ranking are registered in competition C and seeded by ranking R . The scheduler C generates games. The games are assigned a result by the solver S . Then the games are used by R to update the ratings of all involved players. This is repeated ' D ' time.

Section 4.2 explores deeper the behavior observed in the Single Elimination Bracket. Section 4.3.2 explains the snake scheduler. Sections 4.4 and 4.5 compare state-of-the-art rating systems in the snake tournament and the reverse state scenario.

4.2 Elo prediction and the single Elimination Bracket

In November 2023, I presented part of my work to Prof. I. Manolescu. I wanted to have some feedback about the way I performed simulation. During this meeting, he pointed out the long-term rank correlation value of the "Elo on the Single Elimination Bracket" in figure 4.1. It is slightly below what is observed in other formats tested. He suggested I investigate with a small population ($n=8$ players). I followed his advice, and it provided a first formal identification of *matchmaking overfitting*. This is fascinating as the Elo, and the single elimination bracket are two of the most famous, used and studied algorithms in competition, yet what is next presented is never mentioned nor considered.

4.2.1 Formal approach

The problem, when doing simulation with a small number of players, is that the distribution of levels has a massive impact on the ranking behavior. The importance of a *population model* becomes key. You cannot simply draw values from a distribution - the sample size is too small to be representative.

⁵Repeated Self Seeding Competition

I decided to fix a *smooth* probability table (see appendix C.1). The model maintains a strict transitive relationship between the players. If $\mathbb{P}(A \text{ wins against } B) > 0.5$ and $\mathbb{P}(B \text{ wins against } C) > 0.5$ then $\mathbb{P}(A \text{ wins against } C) > 0.5$.

For $n=8$ players, there are $\frac{n!}{2^{n-1}} = \frac{8!}{2^7} = 315$ different initial seedings. One may think that with 8 players, you have $8!$ different way to sort them. But a single elimination tree is a binary tree, with a lot of structural symmetries, and the model does not make a difference between a confrontation " p_1 versus p_2 " and " p_2 versus p_1 ".

In each possible seeding, I computed for each player the probability to win the tournament and the expected score. The score is to be understood as the number of wins. For 8 players, the possible scores are '0' (for an elimination in the first round), '1' (for a win in the first round, and a loss in the 2nd), '2' (two wins and losing the final), and '3' for winning all games and the tournament.

For every seeding, we can then establish theoretical rankings, one based on the probability to win the tournament, and one based on the expected score of each player.

What can come as a surprise, is that for certain seedings, these two rankings are different from the consensus ranking implied by the model. The best player in the model is the favorite to win the tournament in 305 seedings out of 315. He has the highest expected score in 221. The Consensus Ranking, the Ranking of win probability, and the Ranking of expected score are three distinct from each other. Figure 4.2 shows rank correlation between statistical performances implied by seeding versus the model consensus ranking⁶.

Figure 4.2: In the single Elimination Bracket, seeding can impact player's performances. The histogram shows the distribution of Kendall tau rank correlation between statistical ranking and the model consensus ranking. For 8 players we have 315 different seeding. The question is: for a dataset resulting of a seeded single elimination bracket, what does Elo, Glicko, TrueSkill etc. learn - The WinProb, ExpectedScore or the Consensus Ranking?

My conclusion is that a game generator⁷ leads to different interpretations of what "good" means. These meanings can be compared with rank correlation.

⁶More detail in the notebook 'WinningSebProb'

⁷There is no rating system, there is no game data. There is a player model and a scheduler here.

4.2.2 Motivation & goals

The proposed experiment is an illustration of matchmaking overfitting in a typical data formulation. The goal is to produce a biased dataset based on the conclusion in 4.2. The bias introduced should be the sole consequence of the interaction of a scheduler with a ranking, an interaction that exists fundamentally in any competition. The algorithm chosen is Elo. Elo has a proven unique stationary distribution for random and skilled based matchmaking. It does converge to the consensus ranking. For a competition with elimination, there is no such proof.

The idea behind the analysis is that on one side, I evaluate the ranking from a strict empirical point of view: here is a dataset, here a ranking algorithm, how does it perform? Alternatively, using the power of simulation, I generate every encounter never seen in the dataset. For each of these data points, I ask the model about the "real relationship" between the two involved players: Who is better? What is the probability that $player_1$ beats $player_2$? Then I ask the trained ranking to make a prediction for each of these data points *outside of the matchmaking domain*. Finally, the question is, how does prediction on the evaluation set compare to the prediction of data never seen?

The evaluation method I used is the one presented by Valve for their *regional ranking*. It is a common empirical practice. A ranking is trained with games played before a certain date, then evaluated on games played after that date. The measure used is win probability. Each data point prediction is grouped in bins of a given range. For example, if the range is 5%, the bin 50% contains all the games for which $47.5\% \leq prediction \leq 52.5\%$. We say that the **Expected win rate** is 50% for these games. The **Observed win rate** is simply the number of wins divided by the number of game in the bin. The Figure4.3 and its caption were taken directly from valve's GitHub⁸. For the *never seen data point* outside the matchmaking domain, I compare the prediction of the ranking directly with the probability of the solver.

Figure 4.3: Image and caption are from Valve's Regional Ranking GitHub: "There's a strong relationship between expected and observed win rates. The correlation between the two (Spearman's rho in this case) is 0.98. But the slope is shallower than we'd like—in an ideal world, the slope of this line would be closer to 1. The current model tends to underestimate win rates at the low end and overestimate at the high end."

⁸https://github.com/ValveSoftware/counter-strike_regional_standings

4.2.3 Protocol

Considering the Bradley-Terry model, we generate $n=64$ players with a constant level, the game mode is "one-versus-one", and the solver is the LogSolver. The scheduler is a Single Elimination Bracket tournament seeded by an Elo ranking. We perform the *RSSC* loop with $depth = 1000$. Between two tournament editions $event_i, event_{i+1}$, the ranking is updated with the games played in $event_i$, and then used to seed $event_{i+1}$. This produces a dataset of $depth * (n - 1) = 1000 * 63 = 63'000$ ordered games.

For evaluation, we consider 4 moments $m = 200, 400, 600, 800$. For each of these moments we generate a training set with games played up to the tournament $event_m$, and a test set with all games played after it. We then train and evaluate an Elo ranking.

As a remark, the evaluation could have been done during the simulation process. We can ask the ranking to make predictions on the games before the updates. The choice to split the simulation from the evaluation was made to have a more realistic empirical approach. I can upload my dataset on the internet, someone else can download it and evaluate his ranking on it. The data production is strictly separated from the system evaluation (here the Elo ranking).

4.2.4 Results

Figure 4.4: Empirical versus Simulation evaluation. The figure shows results in simulation at $m=200$. On the left, "Expected versus Observed" measure - dots are bins of games. On the right, "Expected versus Ground Truth" - each dot is single game $(player_i, player_j)$ absent from the training and the evaluation sets. Although we have an empirically perfectly tuned ranking, it fails to correctly capture every possible encounter. Indeed, we can observe $(0.5, 0.0)$ & $(0.5, 1.0)$ dots, which means the ranking believes some games are balanced when in fact one of the players has a 100% chance to win the encounter.

All 4 moments of evaluation show similar results, Figure 4.4 displays only one of these moments $m = 200$, the complete figure is available in appendix C.2. First, we can note that from an empirical point of view - *Expected versus Observed Win Rate*, the ranking is perfectly tuned. This should not be a surprise; it is a synthetic dataset; players do not have notions of injury, mental form; they have a constant level. The

game is perfectly balanced, there is no home or away advantage, no referring interference and no cheater. When the ranking is asked to make predictions on confrontations that are neither in the training nor the test set, we can see that most of the most predictions match with the model probabilities (around the identity $x = y$).

However, there are some outlier points. The ranking predicted a 50% win chance for several games where the real probability, the one computed by the model in simulation, is close to 0 or a 100%. The ranking confuses balance game with guaranteed win.

4.3 The Snake format

The first experiments (section 4.2) gives an illustration of matchmaking overfitting possibilities, but in a very specific context that has limited practical impact⁹. A common scheduler for online video games is skilled base matchmaking. For a better gaming experience, customers are matched with each other based on their levels. They have similar expected win and lose chances. Can we have a skilled based matchmaking where the consensus ranking does not perfectly align with the expected score or the win probability ?

4.3.1 Motivation & goals

As scheduler, competitions have a massive upside compares to live matchmaking. It has a start and an end, with an upfront defined amount of games. In live matchmaking, there is no starting nor ending point. The amount of game is at the will of participants. For simulation, this implies a notion of time, a model for players to connect and disconnect. We need moods, effects of game results on intention, etc. All these are yet irrelevant regarding the research question, which just focuses on the interdependency of ranking and scheduler.

The Snake format is an attempt to avoid over-modeling. It has a start, an end, and a defined number of games in which participants face opponents of expected similar level. I do not claim inventing it. I have seen it used in two separate context, a cooking show¹⁰, and at the 2024 Olympics games in Paris for fencing during modern pentathlon¹¹. I have seen no documentation nor reference - I do not know its *official* name¹². I refer to it as the "*snake*" format. There is a big difference between the usage in my simulation and the previously mentioned events: I used it as a stand-alone competition, not as a stage of a bigger event.

4.3.2 Definition

The format takes as input n seeded participants and produces $n-1$ direct confrontation in a single elimination fashion. The loser of each game is eliminated and does not play further.

The first game involves the seed n versus the seed $n-1$. In the second game, seed $n-2$ faces the winner of the first game, and so on. This gives us a recursive formula/algorithm.

⁹Maybe the ATP circuit in Tennis can relate to it. It consists mostly in single elimination brackets and a closed environment with a ranking learning and seeding the circuit.

¹⁰https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Saison_14_de_Top_Chef#Parcours_des_candidats_dans_Top_Chef:_la_Brigade_cachÃ1'e

¹¹https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Modern_pentathlon_at_the_2024_Summer_Olympics#Format

¹²The snake is what the Wikipedia refers to as the 'bonus round', adaptation of the ladder format.

$$\begin{aligned}
Game_1 &:= (Seed_{n-1} \text{ versus } Seed_n) \\
Game_2 &:= (Seed_{n-2} \text{ versus } Winner_1) \\
&\vdots \\
Game_i &:= (Seed_{n-i} \text{ versus } Winner_{i-1}) \\
&\vdots \\
Game_{n-1} &:= (Seed_1 \text{ versus } Winner_{n-2})
\end{aligned}$$

$\forall i = 1, \dots, n-1$, where $Winner_i$ is the winner of $Game_i$. For example $Winner_1$ is either $Seed_n$ or $Seed_{n-1}$.

4.3.3 Properties

The format is interesting regarding many aspects. It is important to mention and illustrate them as part of the model documentation process (see step 6, section 2.1.3). These properties should not be forgotten when designing scenarios or interpreting experimental results.

- **(A) Standing - Ranking:** The result of a tournament is a ranking with no tie. At first place stands $Winner_{n-1}$, 2nd is $Winner_{n-2}$ and $Winner_{n-3}$ completes the podium. $Loser_1$ finishes last of the event.
- **(B) Skilled Based Scheduler:** every game is played between opponents of expected similar skill. $Seed_i$ faces $Winner_{i-1}$. Similar skill here means: each player faces the *single undefeated prior weakest opponent*. In every game, a player faces the "best-weakest" opponent.
- **(C) Winner Probability Bias:** The probability for a $Player_i$ to win the competition is a function of his Seed. For every player, the lower his seeds, the lower his chance to win the competition is.
- **(D) Expected Score Bias:** Unlike the Win probability, the expected score of a Player increases with lower seed.
- **(E) Deterministic Convergence:** Whatever bias (C) and (D) introduce. It is limited to a single tournament edition. Because the final standing is a ranking, we can use it to seed the next tournament edition. Doing so, assuming a Bradley-Terry Model and deterministic run¹³ the final standing of the Nth event is the *Consensus Ranking*.
- **(F) Probabilistic Convergence:** The statement (E) is reasonable for a probabilistic run as well.

(A) is a choice. The final standing of a competition's format can be arbitrary. In this case, to rank participants based on the moment they lost is intuitive to me. There is an alternative, to rank them based on the number of wins. But it has the downside of many ties. The choice induces (E) & (F). (B), (C) and (D) are properties that highlight why the format is of interest in the context of *matchmaking overfitting*. It sets the snake in continuity of the *Elo versus the Single Elimination Bracket* formal approach.

The convergence properties are, however, important for the simulation. It validates the model as a scheduler, at least in runs where the convergence state or ranking is measured. I provide a proof of (E). Proving (F) is harder and requires mathematical skills that I am not enough comfortable with. I leave it as a conjecture. I show that it does indeed happen in a simulation run (see validation in section 4.3.5).

¹³the winner of every game is the player with highest strength

4.3.4 Convergence proof

The proof is harder to read and understand than it actually is. In fact, it is a pretty simple observation. Some of the issues come from my formalism choices, but some come from the terminology in the field of competition. Indeed, when speaking, one would refer to a better or stronger player, and low or high seeds. The best player, is the number 1, and the highest seeds is the 1. As a value (indices in the proof), 1 is small, the smallest of all. This leads to confusing usage of inequalities. Following the proof may require some mental gymnastics, that would not occur in the oral form.

This section is here for the sake of completeness. If equations are not your cup of tea, you can refer to the validation section 4.3.5 where I demonstrate in simulation the convergence properties.

Theorem 1. *Let us consider a population of n ordered players $Player_1, \dots, Player_n$ such that $Player_i$ always wins against $Player_j$ if and only if $i < j$. We consider the snake format as described in section 4.3.2, and play n edition. $Seed_i^k$ represent the Player at seed i in the k -th edition. $Place_j^k$ represent the player that finished at the j -th place in the k -th edition as proposed in 4.3.3 (A).*

claim: *For any arbitrary initial seeding $\mathcal{S} := \{Seed_1^1, \dots, Seed_n^1\}$, and the seeding procedure $Seed_j^i = Place_j^{i-1}$, we have the final standing $\mathcal{F} := \{Place_1^n, \dots, Place_n^n\}$, where $Player_i = Place_i^n \forall i = 1, \dots, n$*

In other words, the players sort themselves out, by skills/strength/levels.

Proof. By induction on k .

Hypothesis: $Player_j = Place_j^k \forall j \leq k$.

Base Case: For $k = 1$, after the first edition $Player_1 = Place_1^1$ This is indeed true, $Player_1$ is by definition the best player and wins against anyone else, i.e. independently of his initial seed. Precisely, if $Player_1$ has $Seed_m^1$, then he wins every games against $Seed_{m+1}^1, Seed_{m-1}^1, \dots, Seed_1^1$. He thus finishes first place, i.e. $Place_1^1$ in the final standing.

Induction Step:

$Player_{k+1}$ wins against any $p \in \{Player_i \mid k+1 \leq i\} = \{Seed_i^{k+1}\} \setminus \{Player_i \mid i \leq k+1\} = \{Seed_i^{k+1} \mid k+1 \leq i\} \implies Player_{k+1}$ is $Winner_{n-k-1}$.

$Player_{k+1}$ loses against any $p \in \{Player_j \mid j \leq k+1\} = \{Place_j^k \mid j \leq k+1\} = \{Seed_{k+1}^k \mid j < k+1\} \implies Player_{k+1}$ loses against $Seed_k^{k+1}$

i.e. $Player_{k+1} = Place_{k+1}^{k+1}$

□

4.3.5 Model Validation

I illustrate the following Snake properties: (B) *Skilled Based Scheduler*, (E) *Deterministic Convergence*, and (F) *Probabilistic Convergence*. I show that the Snake competition is a skilled based Scheduler in which players are naturally¹⁴ sorted by strength.

The claims (C) and (D) are important to understand the motivation and idea behind the scheduler design. However, I cannot provide a good illustration of it. This would require a meaningful metric. There is not one because, well, the matchmaking overfitting is a hypothesis proposed by this thesis. Expected Score and Win probability are problematic because they are defined for competition, not matchmaking. Also, many ranking, including TrueSkill update ratings continuously, one after the other, there is no notion

¹⁴without the help of an external ranking

of game batches, which is necessary for these two metrics. They require knowledge measuring the bias of a dataset. It is a potential (challenging) future work. This is not an issue for simulation run. The general assumption is that matchmaking does not introduce bias in a game dataset. Whether the Snake format introduces one or not is irrelevant regarding the run itself nor the generated data. It is relevant when interpreting results. Independently of what is observed, no conclusion can be made regarding a *learned bias*¹⁵ as this would assume the existence of such bias! But observations could provide evidence that there is or not a bias.

Figure 4.5: The graph shows Kendalltau rank correlation between the final placement of a snake edition and the consensus ranking. The k -th edition (on the x-axis) was seeded with the final placement of the $(k-1)$ -th edition. In orange, a simulation run using the probabilistic *LogSolver* solver, in blue the deterministic *BetterWin* solver. Runs are performed with $n=64$ players of constant levels *BetterWin*. We can see that indeed, after n editions (64) the correlation is at 1, the final standing is the consensus ranking. In the probabilistic case, we can observe a similar converged state, noisy due to the unpredictable nature of a balanced game. A 0.95 rank correlation is a value close to what is observed for any other scheduler (c.f. Figure 4.1).

The figure 4.5 illustrates the convergence of the Snake final standing in the *rssc* protocol. The behavior observed is not different from the one of a ranking algorithm such as the Elo in a round-robin environment. The claim that the format sorts itself the player based on their strength is correct, in the context of deterministic and stochastic simulation. The players are sorted accordingly to the consensus ranking without external intervention.

Figure 4.6 shows the game quality produced in Snake competition as perceived by common competitive ranking algorithms. In the case of TrueSkill and PlackettLuce, the quality was measured using the

¹⁵alternatively: *not learned bias*

built-in `quality()` method. For Elo and Glicko, I implemented the `quality_1vs1()` method from <https://github.com/sublee/glicko/blob/master/glicko.py>

The question that I address with this graph is **not** if the Snake Scheduler is a skilled based competition¹⁶. What we are interested in here is whether ranking algorithms and the format have a similar notion of **balanced matching/pairing**. We can see that in the case of Elo and Glicko, each game is of quality approximately 1.0, this means that both opponents have about 50% chance each to win the game. We have extremely balanced games. This is mostly true for PlackettLuce and TrueSkill, but we can note a few games of weaker quality (below 0.8). These two rankings rate players using a Gaussian (μ , σ). The `quality()` method is not just a function of the difference in both ratings but also in the absolute value of sigma. Take a close look at the below equations.

$$\text{TrueSkill.quality}([[(\mu = 25, \sigma = 8.333)], [(\mu = 25, \sigma = 8.333)]] = 0.4619 \quad (4.1)$$

$$\text{TrueSkill.quality}([[(\mu = 25, \sigma = 0.789)], [(\mu = 25, \sigma = 0.789)]] = 0.9825 \quad (4.2)$$

Both equations show the computation of a TrueSkill game quality between two players of identical ratings. In 4.3.5 it is the default rating¹⁷ and in 4.3.5 it uses ratings with the default μ value, but a σ ¹⁸ value close to what is observed at the end of the simulation in figure 4.6. As time passes, TrueSkill consider the scheduler's games more and more balanced¹⁹.

Figure 4.6: Game quality in the snake format as perceived by different rating systems. The snake format can be seen as a skilled based scheduler because most games are considered balanced by state-of-the-art rating systems.

¹⁶This is by design

¹⁷when the player is new and the system has not been update on any games

¹⁸A simple statistical analysis of the sigma distribution

¹⁹the trueskill rating is said to represent the strength of a player as gaussian distributed value. This observation suggest me that the sigma behave as a confidence value

4.4 Random Snake Experiment

4.4.1 Motivation & goals

The goal is to understand what a ranking learns in a skilled based scheduler. Conceptually, I do not see what information there is in a perfectly balanced game. I say none. I say there is nothing to learn. If you toss a fair coin with friends, you do not draw any conclusions. Maybe after ten losses, you start to believe that the coin is biased, or your opponent is a cheater. But a head or tail says nothing.

The idea in the random snake setup is to present, to a ranking, games that are assumed to be fair are indeed fair. Now if you paid attention in the previous section, the snake is a ranking, and it has some degree of correlation between the initial seeding and the final placement. The bias introduced is more subtle here. All possible matchups are perfectly balanced in a coin toss game. The scheduler will generate a fraction of the possible encounters, and the choice relies on the ranking. We study strictly the interaction of ranking and scheduler. The player model does not exist, any possible game is equivalent and any game outcome is equally likely.

It is a conceptual setup. It makes no sense to organize a tournament of coin toss. Likewise, it makes no sense to speak about skilled base matchmaking for a game with no skill, and certainly no one would build a ranking from such a dataset. But I invite readers, to think about it. What do you believe a ranking means in this context? What metric would you track? I invite the readers to make a guess. How does your favorite ranking algorithm behave in this setting?

4.4.2 Protocol

I perform a comparative study on Elo, Glicko, TrueSkill and Openskill (PlackettLuce). The metric of evaluation is rank correlation with a win rate based ranking²⁰. The simulation parameters are the following ones: parameters:

- players: 64 players
- game type: one-versus-one
- Scheduler: Snake
- Solver: FlipCoin (player level does not matter, pure random results)

For each ranking I perform an RSSC run of depth 500. At different time of the simulation $t=0, 5, 10, 50, 100, 200, 500$, for each player, I measure the total number of wins, the win rate in career, and the win rate over the last 50 played games. This serves as references to compute three different "ground truth" rankings. During the RSSC loop the state²¹ of the ranking is stored after each update, i.e. after each Snake edition.

4.4.3 Results

From a far distance, we can see in figure 4.7 that Elo and Glicko behave similarly, chaotic lines crossing each other multiple times. TrueSkill and PlackettLuce have more straight lines and fewer crossing.

At any point of the simulation, Elo and Glicko have a high rank correlation with the current win rate of the players. The ranking does not converge, it continuously changes. As time passes, it reaches close to 0 rank correlation with its prior states. In a random game, 'skill' means luck.

²⁰Choosing a good metric in this setting is a challenge. The win rate has the benefit that it is practically computable and that it is something that player and spectator of a competition do experience.

²¹the point of each player as computed with their respective ratings

Figure 4.7: Kendall tau rank correlation of state-of-the-art ranking algorithm with observed statistics in the random snake setup. The rows are Algo1=Elo, Algo2=Glicko, Algo3=TrueSkill, Algo4=PlackettLuce. Columns are ranking references computed on wins in the simulation. Colors represent the different moments where the references were computed. For example, the pink line in the top left diagram is the rank correlation of the Elo through time with the final number of wins. We can see that at the beginning of the simulation, the correlation is 0, obviously because little games have been played, and at the end, when all games were played, the correlation is 0.8. This can seem obvious, but compare it with what happens in TrueSkill or OpenSkill.

Regarding TrueSkill and PlackettLuce, the rankings do not change over time. They converged to a state. Onward, the state barely evolves. In skilled based matchmaking and perfectly balanced game, the ranking state is not altered.

In my eyes, both behaviors are reasonable. Exploring every possible ranking state because there is no ranking is acceptable. It means every state is equally 'true/likely', fair enough. And for the second, like I said, in my mind there is no information in a skilled based matchmaking, so the ranking state should not change. This is perhaps the greatest contribution of my thesis: A conceptual test that shows qualitative (not quantitative) differences between well-known ranking techniques. Usually we can read comments like *A converges faster than B, C does better prediction than D* etc. Here we can answer the question: What do they do ?

But there is one thing that bothers me a lot. The state OpenSkill and TrueSkill adopt is not one where players all have the same level. The state the TrueSkill and PlackettLuce adopt is the initial luck. There is no reason to converge initially; the matchmaking quality has not changed. The players' levels did not evolve. After players have each participated in 500 games and more, they are still ranked the same way they were after approximately 10. Why bother playing?

For sure, players realize that they play a bunch of random games, and that higher-ranked players are not better than them. For sure, they get frustrated about the rank difference. I would personally create a new account. Instead of playing 500 games, I would create 50 accounts and play 10 games on each. I would probably get lucky in some of these accounts and get a high rating. I would then play on that account with my ratings not changing much and just brag about my rank! And I would never speak about accounts where I got unlucky and had a low rating.

Maybe I am too far in conclusions. But I think it can be interesting to explore the correlation in video games between the ranking behavior displayed in this experiment, and the number of smurfing accounts.

Another interesting thing to do, is the work on metrics to track. For example, we can measure the elasticity of the system with the difference between the highest and the lowest rated player. We can measure the distribution of game quality over the entire domain, not just the one presented to the ranking.

4.5 Convergence in the Snake format

4.5.1 Motivation & goals

A natural extension is to see how the ranking behavior in the random snake setup translates into a more realistic scenario. We consider a situation where the notion of ranking is meaningful, where players do have an actual in game level.

One parameter is the state of ranking itself. One question is how rankings evolve from a "wrong" state to a more correct one. The worst-case scenario is when the best player has the lowest ratings and the weakest player the highest. That state can be obtained by letting a ranking converge to the consensus ranking and then applying a permutation on the players and reassigning corresponding ratings. This can challenge rankings learning in skilled based matchmaking because, when reversing the ranking, we do not change much the game balance in the snake format.

4.5.2 Protocol

I perform a comparative study on Elo, Glicko, TrueSkill and PlackettLuce. I had one more ranking to the pool, the final standing of the snake competition - players sort them-selves out. The metric of evaluation is rank correlation with the consensus ranking. In the middle of the simulation rankings are applied a permutation where player at rank $i = 0, \dots, n - 1$ receive the rating of player at rank $n - 1 - i$. The ranking is reversed. The experiments is repeated for different population sizes.

parameters:

- players: 8, 16, 32, 64, 128, 256, 512 of constant level
- game type: one-versus-one
- Scheduler: Snake
- Solver: LogSolver

I perform an RSSC loop, and the duration of the simulation is depth=150 Snake tournament editions before the permutation and depth=150 afterward.

The resulting games are stored in $7 \text{populations} \cdot 5 \text{rankings} \cdot 2 = 105 \text{datasets}$ the smallest one contains 2100 games and the biggest 230'000.

4.5.3 Results

Figure 4.8: Kendall tau rank correlation (y-axis) of state-of-the-art rankings with the consensus ranking over time (x-axis, the number of tournament editions). The columns are Algo1=Elo, Algo2=Glicko, Algo3=TrueSkill, Algo4=PlackettLuce. The last column is the final placement ranking in the last completed tournament. Rows are Scheduler. I added Single Elimination and Double Elimination Brackets for comparison purposes. Colors represent the different population sizes. A continuous line indicates the "before" reversing the ranking. The dotted line indicates the behavior after the reversing the ranking. This is why dot starts usually with a rank correlation close to -1.

As we can see in the figure 4.8. In the base case (continuous lines), the rankings converge fast to the consensus ranking. In the Snake format, they all reach a rank correlation around 0.9. Simply put, rankings do what they are supposed to do. They rate and order players based on their skills.

In the Single Elimination Bracket, the correlation is lower, around 0.75-0.8. This should not come as a surprise. Section 4.2 shows how the bracket affects a dataset and the learning of the Elo. From this picture, we can see that the rank correlation of Glicko, TrueSkill and PlackettLuce is consistent with the Elo in the same setting.

Where things get interesting is when we look at the dotted lines, the 'worst case scenario' when rankings are reversed and intentional put at around -1.0 rank correlation. We can see that it takes significantly more time for TrueSkill and PlackettLuce to reach the consensus ranking. Elo and Glicko need less time, fewer games to capture the real level of the participants. To put into perspective the performances. Take a look at the dark blue dotted line; 8 players are sorted in reverse order, the better player is rated the worst. It takes TrueSkill more than 90 snake editions to sort them, this period consists of about 630 games. 630 games were played among 8 players, facing each other again and again.

If you look at the "previous Rank" in the same context, the 8 players are sorted in less than 10 editions. This setting is without a ranking intervention, it is when we use the final placement as seeding for the next edition. Basically, players sort themselves out naturally faster than in a TrueSkill environment. This shows the *hard-stuck* and *boosted* players problematics as a strict consequence of the interaction between a ranking algorithm and a scheduler.

5

Survey

The thesis motivation is based on community complaints. The goal is not just to find answers, but to find ones that can be heard by the community. An important step is to verify if the methodology used is something accepted and understood by people whose job is impacted by ranking and matchmaking systems. A survey was conducted in that regard. The topic of this chapter is the perception of experts on simulation based research.

5.1 Goals & Design

The goal of the study is to measure to what extent simulation based methods can be used to perform research accepted by actors in competition. The survey involves a panel - 4 persons with expertise in different fields of professional competition (in a broad sense). It is performed in three steps.

- **Step 1: Prior Knowledge** In a Google form, participants are asked general questions about who they are, what they know and what they believe in. There is no right or wrong answer.
- **Step 2: Simulation based experiments** Models, Simulation and the experiences of chapter 4 are presented in a series of five videos.
- **Step 3: Learning and Feedback** Finally, in a 2nd Google form, participants are asked questions about the content presented in step 2. Do they understand the model, the experiment? What do they think of certain choices made, like the metrics of interest? Do they accept the work as knowledge? did they learn something?

All the material was produced in French. The content presented is technical, and the experiments abstract. It is hard to present it accurately to an audience with diverse education and knowledge. I relied on intuition to express concepts like *Convergence* and *stationary distribution*. This is easier to do in the mother tongue, French in my case. France is the 7th biggest video game market¹ both in revenue and player base. I do not believe the language choice is detrimental to the results' relevance.

¹<https://newzoo.com/resources/rankings/top-10-countries-by-game-revenues>

5.2 Content Presented

The work is introduced in five videos uploaded on YouTube², each lasting for approximately 8 to 10 minutes. The videos are unlisted and can only be watched with a link.

The first video introduces the basics of simulation based research in the context of competition. I present The Bradley-Terry Model and the consensus ranking. I mention that I believe it is a valid but not frequently used methodology of research in the field. I explained that I have developed my own tool, and showed the basic code usage (Figure 3.4). I do not go into the details of the simulation methodology. However, I insist that the goal is not to draw conclusions about the real world but about a system under study.

In the 3rd video, I introduce the Kendall tau rank correlation, how to read the values, and give some examples. The video also presents the Snake format with its claimed properties.

Each of the sections 4.2, 4.4, and 4.5 are presented in three dedicated videos. Viewers are informed about the model, the parameters, the synthetic dataset generated, and the metric of interest. I briefly motivate the experiment - what are we trying to see, which questions are we asking? I then present the results in one picture. I give the necessary information to read the picture so that the participants can make their own interpretation.

Participants are **NOT** informed about my hypothesis of *matchmaking overfitting*. They are not aware of the steps in a simulation based research. More precisely, they are not presented with the validation steps. They are left with their own intuition and how the Bradley-Terry model fits it.

To understand the survey, it is important to realize that the 3 presented experiments³ can only be performed in simulation. In the real world, the Consensus ranking is not known (I would say does not even exist). Nobody does skilled based matchmaking for Coin Toss, and certainly not a ranking from it. And comparing the model probability versus the observed one is tricky since you only have access to the observation and not the underlying distribution. The experiments show different ranking system behavior. It is not just about a quantitative distinction, but also qualitatively. Something personally, I have not seen in the literature on the subject. Human perspective becomes very interesting when results are not just about numbers.

5.2.1 Questions

In this section, I focus on the general concepts behind the questions and their goals. I do not list every single one of them. The Forms and the results are available as additional material to the thesis for anyone interested in it. In the following text, they/them/their refer to participants.

Who are you? It is asked where their expertise comes from. From which game genre (Tactical Shooters, MOBA, Board game, etc.), and what roles they endorsed (Player, coach, analyst, etc.) Some questions are about their knowledge of the state-of-the-art. Which algorithm they know, which concept they are familiar with. These questions are multiple choices.

What do you believe? There is a set of questions that target directly intuition, values and beliefs about ranking. For example, I ask if they agree with the CETS-215 citation (cf. 1.1). I ask if they believe competition can be manipulated with a scheduler. Most are Yes/No/Maybe questions. The others have the following formulation: *On a scale from x to y, how much do you agree with [...]*. The questions I ask are based on my own intuitions, ideas and opinions. They are the notions I tried to challenge myself on when

²https://youtube.com/playlist?list=PLK9VMh_9P3x1WppFpKXJchYgs39hB5c9V&si=6dbESWSrICoEWUkf

³*Single Elimination Bracket versus the Elo, Random Snake and Snake Convergence*

conducting the research. To some extent, it addresses the foundations of my works.

How to evaluate rankings I ask a precise question regarding features of ranking. These features are related to what ranking is evaluated on in the literature, such as prediction or the speed of convergence. For each feature, they have a choice between: Necessary, Important, Useful, Bonus or Superfluous. I asked them if they are familiar with the methodology in place and how much credit they give to mathematical, empirical, and simulation based studies.

Finally, there is an open question: What are the main challenges research should tackle in matchmaking and ranking?

Participants are asked the same questions in the 2nd form, except for the **Who are you**. The intention is to measure whether the presented research influenced and changed their mind. Additionally, they are asked about each experiment, if they agree with the following statement:

- The experiment was interesting
- The experiment was understandable
- I have learned something
- I have understood something
- I have questioned my ideas
- I remain indifferent

In open questions, they are asked to propose a model or a simulation research question. They also have the possibility to give a general feedback and share feelings about the presented content.

5.2.2 Protocol

Participants were contacted in written forms. They received a similar message⁴, where I present myself. I explain that I am doing a master thesis about methodology in competition. The expert were targeted. Each contact text included a personal paragraph where I explain why I am interested in his opinions.

The material of a step was delivered only after the completion of the previous one. They had the option to do the survey alone but could contact me at any point for clarification and discussion.

The video are single-shot recordings with no post-processing. No montage or sound effect were added. They were presented to a math teacher at the high school level with no particular knowledge of competition to make sure the content is understandable.

Using YouTube, I had access to video statistics such as the number of different viewers and watch time. When delivering material for a step, I did make sure that I received the results of the previous steps, and checked if the watch time increased for each video by their duration.

5.3 Results

The below results come from a panel of 4 participants who completed every step in order. I removed participants who completed the first form but never watched the videos nor answered the 2nd forms.

⁴By email, Discord or Twitter

5.3.1 Initial Form

Participants have experience as coach (1), analyst (2), manager (1), caster (1), content creator (1), tournament organizer (1) or technical background (2). All 4 have stated to be or have been high-level players, and to be passionate spectators. For game genres, they have claimed to be experts in Fighter (1), Shooter (3), and MOBA (1). All participants are familiar with the Elo ranking and skilled based matchmaking. But only one has heard of Glicko, TrueSkill, Stationary distribution, Convergence and Engagement Optimized matchmaking. None of them have previously heard of the Bradley-Terry model or the techniques behind ranking validation. Prior, they slightly favored empirical studies over mathematical ones, but gave limited credit to simulation based research. They do believe it is possible to manipulate competition with an unfit ranking or scheduler, and that regarding the integrity of a competitive ecosystem, both notions are equally important. They also all agree that a ranking design can encourage smurfing⁵ by design. Experts have mixed feelings regarding the *unpredictable nature of competition* but agree that ranking must be based on the player's level. They have mixed, but unclear opinion⁶ regarding the sentence *If one is good, he wins games, on long-term, he ends up ranked accordingly to his level.*

Figure 5.1: Answers to the questions: How important are each of the following features regarding a ranking quality? Blue=Superfluous, Red=Bonus, Yellow=Useful, Green=Important, Purple=Necessary. The features from left to right are: 1) Summarized past success, 2) Predict win probability of encounter, 3) Identify balanced matchups, 4) Identify unbalanced matchups, 5) Fast convergence, 6) Correct ordering based on player level.

Figure 5.1 shows what feature matters for competitive ranking. The panel does not appreciate much the win probability prediction ability. This is what is measured in most research I have read so far. They also do not care much about the correct ordering based on player level, which is what I track with Kendall tau rank correlation. The favored feature **Summarized past success**, that two participants consider **necessary**, is not an ability measured in any paper I have found. Actually, it goes against the evaluation method itself. Usually, a study would split a dataset with a date. The game played before the date belongs to the training set, and the one after is in the test set. Another way to do evaluation would be to split the game before the fixed date into training and evaluation sets. The speed of convergence is a feature the panel is relatively indifferent to.

When it comes to the problems research should look into. One participant mentions the notion of convergence to a 'real ranking' without having been introduced to the consensus ranking, and explicitly

⁵A smurf, is a secondary account to play in online matchmaking. This is usually done by a player who wants to play at another rank than their 'main' account

⁶How much do you agree, on a scale from 1 (not at all) to 10 (absolutely) with the claim? The answers were: 3-4-6-8

says he does not know about the Bradley-Terry Model.

Other consideration:

- For rating purposes, consider individual performance in a team-based game, but be careful not to encourage selfish behavior.
- For which portion of the player base is the ranking optimized? Not the same for top and average player.
- Optimal competition design in different game modes.
- How does the intention of players impact the measures in dataset?

5.3.2 Final Form

In this section I cover the questions about the simulation itself. Not the before and after. The panel did understand how the simulation tool works and the meaning of the Consensus Ranking. They do see what simulation can study that empirical studies cannot. When asked if the model is relevant to competition, one answered no, one maybe and two said yes. The following figure shows the feedback on each experiment.

Regarding Experience 1 'Empirical versus Simulation' where a (single elimination bracket x Elo) dataset is evaluated:

Figure 5.2: Elo, Single Elimination bracket and the expected versus observed win rate. See section 4.2

Regarding Experience 2 'Random Snake', in which players face each other on a coin toss in a skilled based matchmaking:

Figure 5.3: The random snake, described in section 4.4

Regarding Experience 3 'Snake Convergence' where we look at rankings when we reverse their state after convergence in different competition formats:

Figure 5.4: Rank correlation in the snake format, see section 4.5

Figure 5.5: Opinions on simulation based experiments. The colors indicate a degree of agreement. Blue=Absolutely, Red=Mostly, Yellow=Yes, Green=little, Purple=Not at all. The statements in order are: (1) The experiment was interesting, (2) The experiment was understandable, (3) I have learned something, (4) I have understood, (5) I have rethought what I believed in, (6) I remained indifferent. We can see that the panel is interested and learn from simulation based research.

As we can see, the panel found the research very interesting. They understood and learned from the experiments. In figure 5.6, we can see that participants consider the snake model a simple yet interesting format of competition that allows to distinguish ranking algorithms qualitatively. They agree it is a ranking in itself, and that players order themselves long-term wise.

Except one. Someone disagrees with *long-term, players order themselves "naturally" accordingly to their level*. Sure, 'long-term' and 'naturally' are not clearly defined, but I believe the results show clearly the statement. Did the participant really understand the data? Does he see something that I am overlooking? I cannot tell for sure.

The panel is not sure if it is a skilled-based matchmaking nor if it is biased in a single edition. It is worth mentioning that the videos do not include validation steps of the snake scheduler. I do enunciate the properties without supporting it. The shown experimentation does not track metrics that could (dis)prove the statements. For example, I do not present them game quality or rank correlation between seeding and final placement.

Regarding the Snake, did you understand / do you agree with the following statements ?:

Figure 5.6: The Snake Scheduler properties (c.f. 4.2) as perceived by the panel. The colors indicate agreement with statements. Blue=Yes, Red=No, Yellow=Maybe, Green=I do not understand. The statements are: (1) It is a heavily biased format over one edition, (2) long-term, players order themselves 'naturally' accordingly to their level, (3) The results is a ranking, (4) It is a form of skilled based matchmaking, (5) It does represent a player's grinding experience, (6) It is simple enough to understand and interpret what happens, (7) It is interesting to study it, (8) It distinguishes ranking algorithm by their behavior. One participant answered 'do not understand' (green) to each statement. It cannot be concluded from the figure, but can be verified in the data.

Participants are asked if, based on the experiments, they are ready to give an opinion about the usage of the ranking in competition. Two said maybe. Two said yes but did not have the same opinions. One participant rated "Algo1" (Elo) and "Algo2" (Glicko) not well adapted, "Algo3" (TrueSkill) well adapted, and "Algo4" (OpenSkill, PlackettLuce) adapted, but there is better. The other one considers "Algo" 1, 3 and 4 well adapted but qualifies "Algo2" as an ideal one.

Regarding open questions. I received feedback regarding the quality of the survey and the material. Some pictures need better legend, they are not always self-explanatory. The language can be reworked, the balance between technical precision and vulgarization is not perfect. There are a few typos in the Google form as well.

They do propose models and research questions for simulation, as listed below:

- Study many versus many game modes with a high difference in strength of players within teams to see if it leads to player not being ranked accordingly to their level.
- Study win rate percentage of player in game with different meta across different game region

- include intention of player that may not always want to perform at their strength (losing on purpose)

In his feedback, one participant stated:

In my opinion (and a bit of experience), the actors (publisher and devs) do not have to have a balanced game for reasons of dynamism, which I think makes simulation obsolete in numerous cases for which the parameters they themselves would be too unstable.⁷

He mentions the balance of games. In the presented simulation, games are perfectly balanced. In the real worlds, he says it is not the case and considers it an extremely important distinction. I agree, but I want to bring some nuances. Chess is unbalanced. White pieces are slightly favored. But competition is balanced because in double round-robin every opponent faces each other twice, once with the white pieces and once with the black. I disagree that it makes the simulation obsolete. I agree it limits the interpretation. The research is at an early stage, and still abstract. I have my opinions about ranking design, but am still far away from the goal (see section 4.0.2) and resulting conclusions.

I cannot deny that he thinks the simulation obsolete. However, without a direct discussion, what I conclude is the need to model unbalance in games for simulation to be more realistic. In the future, I will definitely include this aspect. I have three different ideas in mind to achieve it. Each will need validation steps, experimentation to identify the standard behavior, and comparative study to understand ranking learning. The challenging part will be to build a reasonable consensus ranking, or alternatively find meaningful metrics to track.

5.3.3 Evolution of Opinion

When it comes to the before and after questions, the **What do you believe in?**, the panel changed their mind. Most of the time, only slightly. There are two points, where the entire panel changed opinion, and visibly so.

About the opinion on simulation. To the question *How much do you give credit to simulation based study*, answer moved from initially (1-2-3-4) to (2-4-4-5) after the videos. And every individual in the panel has a higher opinion on simulation after the survey. They not only believe it is a relevant study tool, but also a potential way to exchange knowledge. To the question *Do you think simulation is a communication tool to share with actors of competition*, two answered maybe, and two said yes. Regarding empirical and mathematical study, they both received four times a grade of 4. With a 5, simulation based study is the only methodology regarded as the best possible approach for ranking in competition by at least one participant in the panel. Before the video, this was clearly not the case.

What also changed is the importance of ranking features as shown in figure 5.7. Past success representation has dropped from necessary to a questionable feature. I do not know why this happened, I did not expect this to change. I do not present any work regarding this aspect of a ranking. Apart from it, the panel has an increased interest in all the other features after watching the videos. *Prediction of win probabilities* and *Correct ordering*, which were considered as bonuses or even superfluous, are now perceived as useful or even necessary. But they remained the least important. The panel is way more interested in the matchmaking balance resulting from ranking usage than the actual ranking state.

5.4 Struggles

I struggled a lot to perform this survey. The first challenge was to select appropriate material to present. My research is still at an abstract level, with a simplistic model and no direct implication to the real world. I

⁷Original quote: De mon avis (et un peu expérience) les acteurs éditeur et devs) n'ont pas a avoir un jeux équilibré pour des raison de dynamisme, ce qui je pense, rend la simulation quaduc dans un grand nombre de cas pour lesquels les parametres eux meme serais trop instable

Figure 5.7: Answers to the questions: How important are each of the following features regarding a ranking quality. Blue=Superfluous, Red=Bonus, Yellow=Useful, Green=Important, Purple=Necessary. The features from left to right are: 1) Summarized past success, 2) Predict win probability of encounter, 3) Identify balanced matchups, 4) Identify unbalanced matchups, 5) Fast convergence, 6) Correct ordering based on player level.

was skeptical that it could be interesting to anyone, expect people with technical knowledge. I am however happy with the end product. The questions are interesting and relevant. The videos are of decent quality.

The submitted answers on Google Forms do not track email addresses, they are anonymous. This limits results interpretation about individuals opinions. I personally know who said what (I can compare the initial and final opinion of a given participant) because I know when participants completed each step. This is not possible for anyone else reading the data. The data tracks the evolution of a panel opinion. Yes, I do have a few interesting insights that I cannot back up⁸. It does not affect much the conclusion of the survey.

Finding participants was a nightmare. By design, it targeted experts in the field, people with solid experience of competition. I cannot remember how many people I contacted with no answer. Some politely declined. One particular explained to me that he receives such survey requests on a daily basis and cannot participate in all of them. I understand the refusal and lack of answer. But it makes it hard. Really hard.

There were options to open the survey. To be more flexible with the targeted participants. Ask anyone with an interest in competition. I did not make this choice. I have a panel of 4 experts. I am interested about opinions of people that ranking and matchmaking impact directly and professionally.

The hypothesis is novel. It is abstract, and the survey material relies on intuition. It is a step-by-step process. Now that I have conducted this survey, I would be excited to redo such work with a broader audience, with no experience restriction. I plan in the future to upload public video on the internet about simulation in more realistic situations, and I think I would like to attach polls to collect opinions and feedback.

5.5 Discussion

I want to discuss some points that may not be obvious at first glance. The panel was consistent in his answers. I presented experiments in triplets (methods, ranking feature, metric). For example, in the first video, I show an empirical analysis of a dataset evaluating win probability prediction using the "Expected versus Observed" technique. In the 3rd video, I present a simulation based study evaluating the ordering of the player with Kendall tau rank correlation. In the formulary, the participants are asked in separate questions their opinion about (A) study methodology, (B) ranking features and (C) metric used. They have simulation and empirical study both in high regard, they give the same amount of interest to the win prediction as they do to correct ordering. Finally, they consider Kendall tau rank correlation with the consensus ranking equally important for a ranking quality as the Expected versus Observed win rate.

The panel did not express opinion about unsupported claims, such as the bias in a snake edition, and whether it is a skilled base matchmaking or not. They answered 'maybe'. It is a very healthy attitude. The panel was not confused by the technicality of the work, by the wordings, or by the experimental setup. They did not see me as an authority and did not believe in everything I said. They kept a critical mind. The panel sample is small, but they provided very good insight.

Players seem to have strong natural ability in modeling. They spontaneously propose features to add and even present a scenario where it is relevant. They are interested and formulate their concerns, doubts and questions in terms of study to perform. They are comparing and are ready to choose their favorite ranking designed based on simulation. It is awesome.

The only participant that had a negative opinion on simulation based research (and consider the model used not suited for ranking study) mentioned his experience in game design. There is only one game designer on the panel. The others have mostly experience as player, coach, analyst and manager. This is interesting. If game designers and competitors do not agree on how to validate ranking, do not have the same perception of what a ranking is, and do not consider the same model valid, then it is not surprising

⁸In the thesis, I only provide result that are readable from the data. I do not share what I cannot back up.

that there are community complaints about ranking and matchmaking quality. There is a disagreement on what the tool is supposed to do. There is a disagreement about what competition consists of.

It does indicate that, maybe, technical work on ranking should try to define more clearly what they mean by a ranking. What it does. Personally, the methodology used in many papers about the Elo ranking fits my intuition based on my personal experience in competition. Methods used to present TrueSkill or OpenSkill do not. I care about the **uniqueness** of a stationary distribution. The methodological differences, and the underlying concept of ranking, inspired most of the design I present in this study. Elo in Chess does not seem to raise many critics.

One learning from my side is the importance of performing such survey in an interactive fashion. When writing the formulary, I paid attention to not formulate question that orients results interpretation. I did not want my own conclusions (and bias) to influence theirs. For example, I asked in step 1 and step 3 *Do you believe ranking can encourage smurfing by design?*. In the final Form I did not ask *In the random snake videos, do you think one of the rankings' behavior encourages smurfing?*, because this leans toward my personal interpretation. All the 4 participants already agreed that rankings can encourage smurfing by designed before watching the videos, nothing changed their minds after. I cannot support my conclusions with their opinions because I did not ask the right question.

Regarding potential future work. I am interested in redoing this exact survey with more participants, not necessary experts. I wonder how the model fits their perception. The material needs to be reworked a bit. I am also very interested in involving experts in the research itself. I wonder in which steps (2.1.3) they can contribute the most. From problem identification to model development and scenario specification, for validation or metrics choices, I have reasons to believe they can contribute at pretty much every step of a simulation based research. The who, when, and how can be a complex research in itself.

6

Conclusion

In this thesis, I show that simple models to simulate competition fit the intuition of experts. They do understand and accept concepts such as consensus ranking and the Bradley-Terry model. They understood and learned from abstract experiments. Likewise, They are capable to propose model's extensions and formulate their concerns in terms of scenarios to investigate. Relevance of simulation based research is as high as other methods. More importantly, the survey shows that they are not tricked into believing unsupported claims. The work highlight the potential to integrate experts at different stage of research in the collaborative fashion.

I propose the matchmaking overfitting hypothesis and provide several examples to identify and define its meaning. In the process, I was able to build a dataset for which a perfectly tuned ranking fails to generalize outside the matchmaking domain. I proposed a conceptual challenge - the random snake - in which state-of-the-art rankings display two different behaviors. I show that this difference translates to differences in convergences when manipulating the initial state. More importantly, I show the hard-stuck and boosted phenomena as the consequence of a rating system in skilled based competition.

Furthermore, my works suggest multiple research priorities. What are good metrics to track in simulation based research? What are the most important components of a realistic model? What does a ranking learn in a dataset? What are the edge cases a rating system should reasonably be able to address? But above all, my work shows the importance of correctly describing the convergence of rating systems and whether it is possible to show a unique stationary distribution. The speed of convergence is less important than the resulting state itself.

Below, a list of my contributions:

- The **RSSC** protocol to study the interplay between a scheduler and a rating system
- The **Snake scheduler** and its properties to study skilled based matchmaking
- The **bias of Single Elimination Bracket**, expected scores do not correlate with athletes' levels.
- The **Random Snake** as a conceptual test for rating system.

The bias of The Single Elimination bracket is likely to have a direct, immediate impact, as The FIFA ranking for football and the Riot Power Ranking put more weight on the final than the first round games.

7

Appendix

Validation

A.1 RSTT version of the 2 player Elo convergence

```
from src.ranking.standard import BasicElo
from src.games import Duel
from src.player import Player
from src.solvers import LogSolver

# initial settings
PlayerA = Player(name='Player A', level=1500)
PlayerB = Player(name='Player B', level=700)

elo = BasicElo(name='Elo', players=[PlayerA, PlayerB])
elo.datamodel.set(PlayerA, 1000)
elo.datamodel.set(PlayerB, 1200)

depth = 1001

# data to track
elo_A, ref_A, elo_B, ref_B = [], [], [], []

# simulation run
for i in range(depth):
    duel = Duel(PlayerA, PlayerB)
    duel.play(LogSolver())
    elo.update(games=[duel])

# data storage
elo_A.append(elo.rating(PlayerA))
ref_A.append(PlayerA.level())
elo_B.append(elo.rating(PlayerB))
ref_B.append(PlayerB.level())
```

Figure A.1: RSTT implementation

B

Performance

B.1 RSSC Protocol

```
from src.player import Player
from src.solver import EloSolver
from src.ranking import BasicElo
from src.competition import SingleEliminationBracket as SEB

# parameters
NB = 512
DEPTH = NB
RANKING = BasicElo
CUP = SEB
SOLVER = EloSolver

# logging parameters
print(NB, DEPTH, RANKING, CUP, SOLVER)

# initialisation
population = Player.create(nb=NB)
ranking = RANKING(name='test performance')
ranking.add(population)

for d in range(DEPTH):
    if d % 50 == 0:
        print(d)
    cup = CUP(name=f'cup {d}', seeding=ranking, solver=SOLVER())
    cup.registration(population)
    cup.run()
    ranking.update(games=cup.played_matches)
```

Figure B.1: Code snippet illustrating the 'rsc' loop. The 'for-loop' executes two high level functionality of the rsc package. Cup.run() generates and plays games. Ranking.update() trigger ranking internal mechanisms that results in a change of it states. This code is a core component of every simulation I perform and present in this thesis.

B.2 Execution Profile

Figure B.2: Output of the command 'pyinstrument -r html rssc.py'. You can note the limited dependencies. It uses the python built-in sort() function. Typeguard is called for typechecking. Names is used to generate random name for the Player instances. All other calls are from within the package.

C

Experiences

C.1 Probability table for the Single Elimination Bracket

The below table show win probabilities of 8 players population (player A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H). A player facing himself has 0.5 chance of winning the game (because he faces someone of identical level). It is a convention - the value is never used in the simulation. The table reads as a matrix $M_{8 \times 8}$ where the value $M_{i,j}$ reads as the probability that 'i wins against j'. It satisfies $\mathbb{P}(i \text{ wins against } j) + \mathbb{P}(j \text{ wins against } i) = 1$ so that there is always one of the player winning the encounter. It also enforces transitivity.

	<i>A</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>E</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>G</i>	<i>H</i>
<i>A</i>	0.5	0.55	0.6	0.65	0.7	0.75	0.8	0.85
<i>B</i>	0.45	0.5	0.55	0.6	0.65	0.7	0.75	0.8
<i>C</i>	0.4	0.45	0.5	0.55	0.6	0.65	0.7	0.75
<i>D</i>	0.35	0.4	0.45	0.5	0.55	0.6	0.65	0.7
<i>E</i>	0.3	0.35	0.4	0.45	0.5	0.55	0.6	0.65
<i>F</i>	0.25	0.3	0.35	0.4	0.45	0.5	0.55	0.6
<i>G</i>	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.35	0.4	0.45	0.5	0.55
<i>H</i>	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.35	0.4	0.45	0.5

C.2 Elo and the Single Elimination Bracket

Figure C.1: Elo performances on the Single Elimination Bracket. Left columns measures 'Expected versus Observed win Probability on data test set. Each point are games grouped in bins of 0.05 probability. Central columns show Expected win probability versus real probability. Each point is a single possible encounter absent from the training set. The right most columns measure the matchmaking quality. Each rows are separate time ($t=200, 400, 600, 800$) in a 1000 events depth simulation.

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